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Board demographic characteristics and cost of debt decisions

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Abstract

We adopt the Agency Theory (1976) as the theoretical foundation of this paper. We estimate the effects of board demographic characteristics on cost of capital of 133 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange for a period of fifteen (15) years, covering 2008 to 2022. Board demographic characteristics considered in this article include, board size, board independence, board meetings, and board gender diversity, while cost of capital is measured by weighted average cost of capital (cost of debt and cost of equity). We use the Generalized Method of Moments to estimate the relationship between board demographic characteristics and weighted average cost of capital. Our regression results suggest that board meetings and cost of capital are positively and significantly related. Additionally, the remaining board demographic characteristics are not significant with cost of capital. The results are limited by sample size. Further research can increase the total sample of companies, or research period. Our results further show that the R^2 is 62 percent. Further research is expected to be able to add other board demographic characteristics that may influence cost of capital decisions. There is also limitations in terms of data and methodology and possible omission of some variables. These findings remain consistent across a series of past results. The insights gleaned from this study will prove beneficial to scholars, management, regulators, and policy-makers.

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Introduction

The high cost of capital in Nigeria has been a source of concern among scholars and policymakers (Ailemen et al., 2014; Akeem et al., 2014; Akinlo & Sule, 2019; Awen & Yahaya, 2023; Ezirim et al., 2017; Ibrahim, 2017; Ibrahim & Ibrahim, 2015; Itopa et al., 2019; Kurniasih & Rustam, 2022; Muritala, 2012; Sdiq & Abdullah, 2022; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021). Capital is an essential part of the requirements for business, therefore, at high cost, it is a serious problem for business stakeholders. In a recent study by Ibrahim and Yahaya (2023), leverage averages 85 percent. In another related study by Samaila et al. (2023), leverage averages 71 percent. The high cost of capital is not good for business for several reasons (1) it raises the selling price of products and services, which may lead to inflation, (2) it reduces revenue due to businesses, because it lowers effective demand, and (3) it may lead to business collapse or failure if preventive measures are not taken early. The cost of capital is a firm's calculation of the minimum return that would be necessary in order to justify undertaking a capital project. A high cost of capital, therefore, reduces investments in assets, which are designed to yield revenue in the future and ensure a stream of cash flow.

There is need, therefore, albeit, urgently to intervene to ensure that the cost of capital is kept at optimum, because, too low cost of capital will not encourage savings, loans and investments. While there are several change agent stakeholders that have been proposed that can intervene and ensure an optimum cost of capital, (1) CEO (Aghazadeh et al., 2018; Huang et al., 2009; Javaid et al., 2021; Iatridis & Senftlechner, 2014; Lui et al., 2016; Mishra, 2014; Shen & Zhang, 2020), (2) ownership structure (Ali-Shah & Butt, 2009; Elston & Rondi, 2006; Ould Daoud Ellili, 2020; Teti et al., 2016), and (3) women directors (Aljughaiman et al., 2022; Arslan & Abidin, 2019; Cimini, 2022; Gjergji et al., 2023; Jun et al., 2023; Richardson et al., 2016; Sarang et al., 2022a; Sarang et al., 2022b; Srivastava et al., 2019), this article looks at the role of board of directors in reducing the cost of capital of the firm.

Board of directors is an organ of the firm, which is part of corporate governance mechanisms, designed to ensure the protection of the shareholders' wealth. A board of directors is the governing body of a firm, whose members are elected or appointed by shareholders (in the case of public companies) to set strategy, oversee management, and protect the interests of shareholders and stakeholders. In a nutshell, a board of directors is a group of individuals who are responsible for overseeing the management and direction of a firm. In this paper, the board of directors is operationalized through its size, independence, gender and frequency of

meetings. The board can influence the firm's cost of capital through increasing the part of profit that is ploughed back into the business, so that little outside capital is needed by the firm, thus reducing the cost of debt component of weighted average cost of capital. Also, an effective board brings confidence among equity shareholders, so that there is no need to demand for higher dividend as an interim measure by equity shareholders, who are afraid of loss of capital gains.

Furthermore, it is true that there are several empirical studies that have examined the role of board of directors in cost of capital outside Nigeria. For example, Ali-Shah and Butt (2009) examine the impact of corporate governance. A total of 114 listed companies were investigated to analyze the relationship between the two variables for the period 2003 to 2007. They found a negative relationship between board size and cost of equity, and a positive relationship between board independence and the cost of equity.

Busru et al. (2019) examine the effect of corporate governance mechanisms on cost of capital in 270 listed Indian firms for period of nine years ranging from 2007–08 to 2015–16, using OLS multiple regression model. The results show that board characteristics were ineffective in reducing cost of capital and debt and equity as well. Furthermore, Javaid et al. (2021) contribute to the existing literature by extending the empirical work on the relationship between corporate governance and capital structure by analyzing the mediating role of cost of capital in the non-financial firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX). The study's findings are that board size and board composition, have statistically significant direct effect on the firm's financing decisions. The interesting finding of the paper is on the evidence of mediating role of cost of capital in the nexus of corporate governance and capital structure. Also, some conventional determinants of capital structure, including the firm's size, profitability, and growth, are found as determinants of capital structure decisions of the firms.

In Nigeria, however, the same cannot be said of works relating board of directors with firm's cost of capital. This article is a novel attempt to fill this gap in the literature. A number of stakeholders, such as scholars, researchers, employees, managers, board members, investors, customers, suppliers, government agencies, labour unions, and communities will benefit from the study. In addition, the expected findings of the study are source of performance improvement and policy improvement. Also, it is expected that the findings would add to the body of knowledge and literature on the subjects: board demographic characteristics and firm's cost of capital. It is also expected that it will aid future research.

In the area of scope, the expected findings are limited to 133 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange. Also, the board demographic characteristics used in this article are limited to board size, board independence, board gender diversity and frequency of board meetings. Furthermore, cost of capital is seen from the point of weighted average cost of capital. In

addition, the data used in this study is limited to 15 years (2008-2022). The methodology is limited to the Generalized Method of Moments. The data are obtained from annual reports and accounts of the firms under consideration, which are part of the requirements by law (CAMA, 1990, as amended 2020). The remaining sections focus on literature review, methodology, results, discussions, conclusions, recommendations and references.

Literature Review

The agency theory propounded by Jensen and Meckling (1976) is the theoretical foundation of this paper. Agency theory explains (1) the relationship between the shareholders and managers, and (2) the relationship between lenders and managers. With the divorce between ownership (principal) and control (agent), there is the likelihood of a clash of interests between the principal and agent. Agency theory comes in to resolve this potential conflict of interests, by ensuring that managers are aware that their tasks are to maximize the shareholders' wealth and protect shareholders' interest at all times in their considerations. The analytical framework of this paper is therefore, premised on the agency theory. Figure 1 illustrates the analytical framework of the paper.

Figure 1. *Analytical Framework*
Source: The Authors (2023)

In this paper, board characteristics are operationalized through board size, board independence, frequency of board meetings and board gender diversity. Similarly, cost of capital is operationalized by weighted average cost of capital. Board size is defined as measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman +Vice Chairman +CEO/Managing director + Executive Directors +Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary. In the same context, board independence is

seen as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%). Furthermore, board meetings is seen as the number of the board meetings held by the board of directors in a year. Similarly, board gender diversity is seen as the number of female directors divided by total board size (%). Also, weighted average cost of capital is defined as the sum of cost of debt multiply by debt weight and corporate tax adjustment plus cost of equity multiply by equity weight (%). In terms of control variables, firm listing age is defined as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange. Similarly, firm size is defined as the natural log of total asset. Firm growth is defined as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%). Finally, firm profitability is defined as return on asset, which is defined as earnings before interest and taxes divided by total asset (%).

In terms of empirical studies, Ashbaugh et al. (2004) examine the nexus between corporate governance and cost of capital and find a negative relation between the cost of equity and the independence of the board. Furthermore, Ali-Shah and Butt (2009) examine the impact of corporate governance. A total of 114 listed companies were investigated to analyze the relationship between the two variables for the period 2003 to 2007. They found a negative relationship between board size and cost of equity, and a positive relationship between board independence and the cost of equity.

Also, Reverte (2009) investigates the relationship between corporate governance and cost of equity capital for a set of Spanish firms. The paper focuses on some board characteristics (board independence and board size) in order to construct a summary corporate governance measure for each firm. Then, by using regression analysis, it examines whether higher governance quality is associated with a lower cost of equity capital. The results show that stronger governance firms have a lower cost of equity capital. In addition, Also, Upadhyay and Sriram (2011) examine the impact of board size on both the equity holders and bondholders by analyzing how board size affects the cost of capital of a firm. Using a sample of S&P 1500 firms, the study finds that board size is positively associated with variables that proxy for cost of capital. Further tests indicate that firms with larger boards pay lower weighted average cost of capital.

Furthermore, Suchard et al. (2012) use a sample of large Australian firms from 1994 to 2003 to show that variation in firm-level corporate governance mechanisms plays an important role in explaining a firm's cost of capital. The empirical results show that greater independent boards serve to reduce the perceived risk of a firm, thereby leading investors to demand lower rates of return on capital provided. Similarly, Mazzotta and Veltri (2014) investigate the relationship between corporate governance and the cost of equity capital based on a sample of companies listed on the Italian Stock exchange on 31/12/2009. The selected CG attributes (board independence and board size) have been used to construct a comprehensive corporate governance quality index for each firm.

The results provide evidence of a significant association between the CG score and the firm's equity capital cost.

Tran (2014) investigates the extent to which corporate governance affects the cost of debt and equity capital of German exchange-listed companies. The results suggest that firms with significant cost of debt effects only in the largest German companies. Also, Elbannan and Elbannan (2015) examine the association between the quality of bank governance mechanisms and cost of capital. The main results show that banks with reported large board size and more executive directors on board are able to obtain finance from cheaper resources. Furthermore, the cost of deposits decreases significantly for banks reporting better governance mechanisms. Arslan and Abidin (2019) examine the relationship between corporate governance and cost of capital based on a sample of listed firms of Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) over the period of 2009–2015. The findings also reveal a significant negative association between CG and COC; hence, firms with higher CG score enjoy a lower COC. Interestingly, gender diversity and board size have a negative association with CG compliance and COC.

Srivastava et al. (2019) construct a comprehensive Indian corporate governance index and analyze its impact on the cost of equity of a firm. The results suggest that among all the sub-indices, board composition predicts the cost of equity to a greater extent. Also, Anwar et al. (2019) investigate the extent to which governance affects firms' cost of equity capital in Asian countries by employing a regression model on panel data of the 24 Asian countries over the period of 2006 to 2015. The results depict that Quality of Corporate Governance (QCG) index has significant relationship in reducing cost of equity for firms in Asian countries. The results also indicate that explicit corporate governance variables like; board independence has significant association with firm's cost of equity in Asian countries which is in accordance with the agency theory.

Busru et al. (2019) examine the effect of corporate governance mechanisms on cost of capital in 270 listed Indian firms for period of nine years ranging from 2007–08 to 2015–16, using OLS multiple regression model. The results show that board characteristics were ineffective in reducing cost of capital and debt and equity as well. Anwar (2020) determines connection of governance mechanisms with cost of capital based on Agency and Stewardship theories for companies in agriculture sector in 20 Asian countries from 2009-2018 for 363 agricultural firms as agriculture significantly contributes in growth of Asian economies. The results depict that variable of corporate governance significantly and negatively affect the variable of weighted cost of capital. Moreover, return on asset and sales growth have significant positive connection with weighted cost of capital whereas, the firm size has significant negative relationship with the weighted cost of capital.

Furthermore, Javaid et al. (2021) contribute to the existing literature by extending the empirical work on the relationship between corporate governance and capital structure by analyzing the mediating role of cost of capital in the non-financial firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX). The study's findings are that board size and board composition, have statistically significant direct effect on the firm's financing decisions. The interesting finding of the paper is on the evidence of mediating role of cost of capital in the nexus of corporate governance and capital structure. Also, some conventional determinants of capital structure, including the firm's size, profitability, and growth, are found as determinants of capital structure decisions of the firms. In Nigeria, however, the same cannot be said of works relating board of directors with firm's cost of capital.

Sarang et al. (2022) examine the relationship between women directors and the cost of equity (COE). Specifically, this study posits that women directors tend to lower the COE. This study uses the US-listed firms' data from 2002 to 2014, comprising 11,189 firm-year observations. This study documents that women directors are linked to the COE. Furthermore, Saleh et al. (2022) analyse the association between board gender diversity and cost of capital. The findings of this study reveal that board gender diversity has a significant negative impact on cost of capital. Salehi et al. (2023) examine the relationship between corporate governance and the cost of equity in Iraq. The statistical sample includes 34 companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2017. Board structure (i.e. board size, board independence, and board meetings frequency) are considered proxies for corporate governance structure. The results suggest that corporate governance structure plays a significant role in reducing cost of equity. Specifically, findings indicate that board size and board meeting frequency are negatively associated with cost of equity.

This article is a novel attempt to fill this gap in the literature. A number of stakeholders, such as scholars, researchers, employees, managers, board members, investors, customers, suppliers, government agencies, labour unions, and communities will benefit from the study. In addition, the expected findings of the study are source of performance improvement and policy improvement. Also, it is expected that the findings would add to the body of knowledge and literature on the subjects: board demographic characteristics and firm's cost of capital. It is also expected that it will aid future research. Based on these mixed results, the following hypotheses are developed and tested:

H₀₁: Board size has no significant effect on cost of capital.

H₀₂: Board independence has no significant effect on cost of capital.

H₀₃: Board meetings has no significant effect on cost of capital.

H₀₄: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on cost of capital.

The remaining sections are devoted to research methodology, results, discussions of the results, conclusions and recommendations.

Methodology

This study uses correlational research design to conduct the study. Although, there are 155 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange website as at 31 December 2022, the sample for this study is the 133 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange for the period of 2008–2022, that is, 22 firms are excluded. The model of this study is adapted from the work of Javaid et al. (2021) and amended to account for the control variables in the model:

$$CC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_{i,t} + \beta_2 BI_{i,t} + \beta_3 BGD_{i,t} + \beta_4 FBM_{i,t} + \beta_5 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_6 FS_{i,t} + \beta_7 FG_{i,t} + \beta_8 FP_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas CC is Cost of Capital, BS is Board Size, BI is Board Independence, BGD is Board Gender Diversity, FBM is the Frequency of Board Meetings, LAGE is Listing Age of the firm, FS is Firm Size, FG is Firm Growth, FP is Firm Profitability, i is Firm Script (in this case, i is 133 firms), t is Time Script (in this case, t is 15 years, 2008-2022), α is Alpha (Constant also known as Intercept), β_{1-8} are Beta Coefficients, and ε is the idiosyncratic error term. The variables are operationalized in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. *Operationalization of Variables and Expected Signs.*

Serial	Variable	Label	Description	
1	Y, Cost of capital	CC	Measured as the sum of cost of debt multiply by debt weight and corporate tax adjustment plus cost of equity multiply by equity weight (%).	
2	X ₁ , Board Size	BS	Measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman +Vice Chairman +CEO/Managing director + Executive Directors +Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary.	-
3	X ₂ , Board Independence	BI	Measured as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%).	-
4	X ₃ , Board Gender Diversity	BGD	Measured as the number of female directors divided by total board size (%).	-
5	X ₄ , Frequency of Board Meetings	FBM	Measured as the number of the board meetings held by the board of directors in a year.	-
6	X ₅ , Listing Age	LAGE	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.	+/-
7	X ₆ , Firm Size	FS	Measured as natural log of total asset.	+/-
8	X ₇ , Firm Growth	FG	Measured as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).	+/-
9	X ₈ , Firm Profitability	FP	Measured as earnings before interest and taxes divided by total asset (%).	+/-

Source: The Authors (2023)

The variables are extracted from the annual reports and accounts, which form part of the financial statements that companies are legally required to produce. The methods of collection

are contents analysis and ratios. Based on 1,995 firm-year observations, the Generalized Method of Moments was applied for the regression analysis of the underlying study, after accounting for descriptive statistics and correlation matrix. GMM is the most appropriate model for panel data, because it takes care of the problem of within and between endogeneity, usually associated with panel data. Furthermore, the F-test is used to test model fitness, while the R^2 is used to explain the degree at which the joint effects of board demographic characteristics and the 4 control variables have on weighted cost of capital. The t-test is used to test the effect of individual variables on WACC.

Thus, our a priori expectations are stated as follows.

$X_1 > 0$, a rise in board size, will lead to a reduction in weighted cost of capital.

$X_2 > 0$, a rise in board independence, will lead to a reduction in weighted cost of capital.

$X_3 > 0$, a rise in board gender diversity, will lead to a reduction in weighted cost of capital.

$X_4 > 0$, a rise in frequency of board meetings, will lead to a reduction in weighted cost of capital.

Results and Discussions

This section of the paper is divided into descriptive statistics (see Table 2), correlation matrix (see Table 3) and regression results (see Table 4).

Table 2. *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
CC	1,995	3.656	2.574	0	13.876
BS	1,995	9.256	3.163	3	21
BI	1,995	73.433	12.994	16.67	100
BM	1,995	4.896	1.751	1	16
BFG	1,995	15.535	13.431	0	66.67
LAGE	1,995	22.44	15.392	2	50
FS	1,995	8.963	.459	8.03	10.77
FG	1,995	27.707	39.235	-65.94	224.98
FP	1,995	1.383	2.862	-20.23	9.54

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

Based on the results in Table 2, the number of observations is 1,995, representing the cross sections (133) firms and time series (15 years). The cost of capital averages 3.656 percent, board size averages 9 members, board independence averages 73.433 percent, frequency of board meetings averages 5 times in a year, and board gender diversity averages 15.535 percent. On the control variables, firm listing age averages 22 years, firm size averages 8.963 times, firm growth averages 27.707 percent, and firm profitability averages 1.383 percent. In terms of the spread, that is, standard deviation, the cost of capital standard deviation is 2.574 percent, which is quite

on the high side ($2.574/3.656 = 70.4\%$) when compared with its mean (average), suggesting that cost of capital is volatile and it requires further investigation, board size standard deviation is 3 members, board independence standard deviation is 12.994 percent, frequency of board meetings standard deviation is 2 times in a year, and board gender diversity standard deviation is 13.431 percent. On the control variables, firm listing age standard deviation is 15 years, firm size standard deviation is .459 times, firm growth standard deviation is 39.235 percent, and firm profitability standard deviation is 2.862 percent.

In terms of the minimum mean, the cost of capital minimum mean is 0 percent, board size minimum mean is 3 members, board independence minimum mean is 16.67 percent, frequency of board meetings minimum mean is 1 time in a year, and board gender diversity minimum mean is 0 percent. On the control variables, firm listing age minimum mean is 2 years, firm size minimum mean is 8.03 times, firm growth minimum mean is -65.94 percent, and firm profitability minimum mean is -20.23 percent. In terms of the maximum mean, the cost of capital maximum mean is 13.876 percent, board size maximum mean is 21 members, board independence maximum mean is 100 percent, frequency of board meetings maximum mean is 16 time in a years, and board gender diversity maximum mean is 66.67 percent. On the control variables, firm listing age maximum mean is 50 years, firm size maximum mean is 10.77 times, firm growth maximum mean is 224.98 percent, and firm profitability maximum mean is 9.54 percent. Furthermore, we conduct correlation analysis and the results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. *Correlation Matrix*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1) CC	1.000								
(2) BS	-0.026 (0.513)	1.000							
(3) BI	-0.064 (0.105)	0.054 (0.176)	1.000						
(4) BM	0.072 (0.075)	0.334* (0.000)	0.002 (0.951)	1.000					
(5) BFG	-0.049 (0.218)	0.115* (0.004)	0.136* (0.001)	0.103* (0.010)	1.000				
(6) LAGE	0.009 (0.825)	-0.054 (0.175)	0.068 (0.087)	-0.013 (0.746)	0.014 (0.732)	1.000			
(7) FS	-0.002 (0.967)	0.062 (0.117)	0.037 (0.349)	0.029 (0.471)	-0.048 (0.222)	0.279* (0.000)	1.000		
(8) FG	0.019 (0.638)	-0.007 (0.856)	-0.039 (0.322)	0.023 (0.560)	-0.024 (0.539)	-0.251* (0.000)	-0.208* (0.000)	1.000	
(9) FP	0.041 (0.305)	-0.037 (0.352)	-0.030 (0.446)	-0.021 (0.605)	0.004 (0.914)	-0.128* (0.001)	0.166* (0.000)	0.066 (0.092)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As shown in Table 3, board size is negatively correlated with cost of capital. Similarly, board independence is negatively correlated with cost of capital. Also, board female gender is negatively correlated with cost of capital. In contrast, however, frequency of board meetings is positively correlated with cost of capital. On the control variables, firm listing age is positively correlated with cost of capital. In the same vein, firm growth is positively correlated with cost of capital. Also, firm profitability is positively correlated with cost of capital. In contrast, however, firm size is negatively correlated with cost of capital. We are conduct regression analysis and the results are contained in Table 4.

Table 4. *GMM Regression Results*

CC	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
BS	-.0296505	.0339557	-0.87	0.383	-.0962023	.0369014
BI	-.0113692	.0081707	-1.39	0.164	-.0273834	.004645
BM	.133909	.0600107	2.23	0.026	.0162901	.2515279
BFG	-.010597	.0072602	-1.46	0.144	-.0248268	.0036328
LAGE	.0028874	.007097	0.41	0.684	-.0110224	.0167971
FS	-.0407917	.2402253	-0.17	0.865	-.5116246	.4300413
FG	-.0014667	.0025254	-0.58	0.561	-.0064163	.0034829
FP	.0385678	.0309179	1.25	0.212	-.0220302	.0991659
/b0	4.566003	2.246109	2.03	0.042	.1637102	8.968296

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

In terms of directions, the results in Table 4 illustrate that board size negative direction in relation with cost of capital. Similarly, board independence shows negative direction with cost of capital. In the same vein, board female gender shows negative direction with cost of capital. In contrast, board meetings show positive direction with cost of capital. On the control variables, firm listing age shows positive direction in relation with cost of capital. Firm size shows negative direction with cost of capital. Firm growth shows negative direction with cost of capital. Firm profitability shows positive direction with cost of capital.

Furthermore, in terms of quantity of effects, for every increase in board size, cost of capital reduces by 2.965 percent, for every rise in board independence, cost of capital reduces by 1.136 percent. Similarly, for every rise in board female gender, cost of capital reduces by 1.05 percent. However, in contrast, for every rise in the frequency of board meetings, cost of capital increases by 13.39 percent. On the control variables, for every increase in firm listing age, cost of capital increases by 0.288 percent, for every rise in firm size, cost of capital reduces by 4.07 percent, for every unit rise in firm growth leads to reduction in cost of capital. However, for every rise in firm profitability, cost of capital increases by 3.8567 percent.

In terms of significance effect, board size has no significant effect on cost of capital. Board independence shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Board female gender shows no significant on cost n cost of capital. However, in contrast, the frequency of board meetings shows significant effect on cost of capital. On the control variables, firm listing age shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Firm size shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Firm growth shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Firm profitability shows no significant effect on cost of capital. These results are mixed, while board size, board independence and board female gender are consistent with our a priori expectations, the frequency of board meetings was expected to be negative but the results turn out to be positive. All the four (4) control variables are consistent with our a priori expectations.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examines the effects of board demographic characteristics on the cost of capital of 133 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, over a period of 15 years (2008-2022), using the GMM approach. The results show that the cost of capital averages 3.656 percent, board size averages 9 members, board independence averages 73.433 percent, frequency of board meetings averages 5 times in a year, and board gender diversity averages 15.535 percent. On the control variables, firm listing age averages 22 years, firm size averages 8.963 times, firm growth averages 27.707 percent, and firm profitability averages 1.383 percent. The correlation analysis shows that board size is negatively correlated with cost of capital. Similarly, board independence is negatively correlated with cost of capital. Also, board female gender is negatively correlated with cost of capital. In contrast, however, frequency of board meetings is positively correlated with cost of capital. On the control variables, firm listing age is positively correlated with cost of capital. In the same vein, firm growth is positively correlated with cost of capital. Also, firm profitability is positively correlated with cost of capital. In contrast, however, firm size is negatively correlated with cost of capital. The GMM regression analysis shows that board size has no significant effect on cost of capital. Board independence shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Board female gender shows no significant on cost n cost of capital. However, in contrast, the frequency of board meetings shows significant effect on cost of capital. On the control variables, firm listing age shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Firm size shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Firm growth shows no significant effect on cost of capital. Firm profitability shows no significant effect on cost of capital. However, there are a few limitations to our study which could be addressed by upcoming research. We did not include all the board demographic characteristics. However, we used only four demographic characteristics, including board size, board independence, board gender diversity, and frequency of board meetings to examine their impact on the cost of capital

choices of the firms. Future studies may fill this research gap by involving some other demographic characteristics of the board of directors. Further, due to the study's limitations, we only tested the direct effects of board demographic characteristics on cost of capital, hence, future researchers can analyze the mediating or moderating roles of different variables which may influence the relationship between board demographic characteristics and cost of capital choices of the firms.

The study has many valuable guidelines and practical implications for the financial managers of the corporations. Our results will facilitate the policymakers in setting their corporate governance policies and practices and making the value relevant capital structure decisions in compliance with the implications of corporate governance mechanism. In addition, our study provides the empirical evidence in accordance with the argument that good governance practices, particularly the voluntary disclosures by the firm may reduce the information asymmetry which, ultimately, reduces the agency cost and the cost of capital for the firm. However, while deciding the financial policy of the corporations, managers can use our findings in order to assess the effectiveness of corporate governance practices employed by the firm in achieving the optimal capital structure at which the weighted average cost of capital is at its minimum level. This paper contributes to the literature by investigating the role of board of directors in reducing the cost of capital decisions of the firms. This paper provides empirical evidence that board demographic characteristics directly affect cost of capital decisions.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest between the authors.

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